

Exploring Machine Learning for Flood Risk Identification: A Case Study of the Tamanduateí River Basin

André Nogueira Sousa,¹ INPE, São José dos Campos, SP

1 Expanded abstract

Flood risk identification is an important challenge in urban planning, especially in populated river basins. The Tamanduateí River Basin, located in São Paulo, Brazil, is an important case study for flood risk due to its urban landscape and historical flood occurrences. Common approaches in flood risk assessment are based on hydrological models and expert knowledge, but recent advances in geospatial data and machine learning have offered new opportunities for flood prediction systems [1, 3].

This study proposes a pattern recognition approach for flood risk classification using geospatial data. Three geospatial datasets from the Tamanduateí River Basin are used in this development: (1) Digital Terrain Model (DTM), providing elevation data at 5-meter resolution, (2) Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) classification with 14 distinct categories, including urban areas, vegetation, water bodies, and agricultural land, and (3) Historical flood occurrence data from 2019, serving as ground truth for classification. The flood occurrence data does not account for the severity or temporal dependency of events. It is binary data that indicates whether a flood occurred in a specific pixel at any point in 2019.

Our ultimate goal is to develop a QGIS plugin that integrates pattern recognition classification algorithms to provide users with a tool for automated preliminary flood risk assessment. This work is part of the INPE Pattern Recognition course and focuses on establishing the analytical foundation for the plugin by comparing different machine learning approaches that will be implemented in the future. In this context, the purpose of this project is to answer the following questions to support the plugin development: (1) How do topographic features from DTM data correlate with flood occurrence? (2) Which land use categories contribute more to flood risk? (3) How do different pattern recognition algorithms compare in their ability to predict flood risk from geospatial features? (4) Which machine learning approaches are applicable for integration into a QGIS plugin? It is important to make it clear that the goal of the study is not to produce high-quality classification models, but to use the model results to identify the features and, consequently, the geospatial characteristics that lead to flood risk.

The methodology adopted includes data preprocessing, algorithm comparison, and planning the development of the plugin, as illustrated in the flowchart in Figure 1. The preprocessing pipeline includes several steps to ensure data consistency and compatibility. First, we implemented an alignment of coordinates using GDAL warping functions to match the resolution and coordinate reference systems from the different datasets. Due to dimension mismatches between datasets (DTM: 32,262,391 pixels vs. LULC/Flood: 32,273,752 pixels), we employed a k-nearest neighbor spatial matching using cKDTree algorithms to align the coordinate systems. The flood occurrence data was converted from point vector format to a raster format that matches the reference DTM resolution. LULC categories are encoded using one-hot encoding to create binary features for each type of land cover.

We implemented and compared multiple classification approaches from conventional pattern recognition theory [2] on this dataset. Bayesian methods, Linear classification methods, and non-linear classifiers based on ensembles and Neural Networks were evaluated. The list of tested algorithms includes: Maximum Likelihood estimation with multivariate Gaussian distributions, Minimum Euclidean Distance classifiers, K-Nearest Neighbors with varying neighborhood sizes, Parzen window density, Support Vector Machines with linear and non-linear kernels, Random Forest, AdaBoost, Voting classifiers, Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLP) and custom-implemented Radial Basis Function (RBF). The applied methods were selected using as a reference the methods proposed in the INPE Pattern Recognition course, given that our aim is for learning purposes rather than achieving the best performance.

¹andrenogsousa@gmail.com

Figure 1. Flood Risk Identification Methodology Flowchart

Each algorithm was evaluated using standard machine learning metrics common in binary classification, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC, with particular attention to handling the class imbalance in flood occurrence data where positive rows represent a small fraction of the total dataset. All implementations utilize the scikit-learn framework.

Our current results demonstrate the potential of applying machine learning algorithms to geospatial data to perform flood risk assessment. The data was preprocessed to integrate 32+ million pixel observations from DTM and LULC datasets, generating the feature space for classification and analysis.

The exploratory analysis showed correlations between elevation and land use with flood occurrence. Areas with lower elevations showed increased flood susceptibility, while certain land use categories (particularly urban and agricultural areas) were demonstrated to have a higher correlation with historical flood events. The preliminary results of the classification algorithms indicate that ensemble methods, such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, achieved better performance when compared to traditional Bayesian and linear approaches. The models successfully identify flood-risk areas and the main features that lead to this result. The main challenge was the class imbalance, as the majority of the dataset belongs to the null class (no flood in 2019). The feature importance calculation from the tree-based models shows that elevation features from DTM data contribute significantly to flood prediction, followed by some specific LULC categories, including urban and deforestation areas.

These analytical findings provided the base for defining which algorithms and features will be suitable for integration into the planned QGIS plugin. The current results indicate that ensemble methods, particularly Random Forest, would be excellent candidates for plugin implementation due to their performance and built-in feature importance capabilities.

Some limitations were identified in the current development. While functional, the spatial alignment approach using nearest-neighbor matching may introduce inaccuracies that can affect the overall analysis. Future work will implement resampling techniques. The current study focuses on a single basin and a unique time period, limiting the analysis to this unique result. Future versions should include multi-temporal analysis, additional basins for validation, and integration with extra data, such as meteorological data including precipitation and temperature variables. The next major phase of this work is the development of the QGIS plugin that will implement the best-performing algorithms identified in our analysis.

References

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